

Agricultural Land Use and Crop Diversification Trends in Hisar District: A Multi-Decadal Analysis (1991-2011)

Surender Kumar, Research Scholar, IEC University, Baddi, Solan, Himachal Pradesh

Email id: surenderchopra72@gmail.com

*Dr. Prem Chand, Assistant Professor, Deptt. of Humanities & Social Sciences, IEC
University, Baddi, Solan, Himachal Pradesh*

Abstract:

Urban expansion has significantly altered agricultural land use by disrupting the traditional farming patterns and indirectly influencing crop selection over time. The farmers face increasing pressure to prioritize high-yield cash crops over diversified farming systems as urbanization encroaches on cultivable land which increases the burden on farmers to balance productivity with limited land area. This study examines the multi-decadal transformation of agricultural land use in Hisar District of Haryana for three census time periods (1991, 2001, and 2011) and simultaneous changes in cropping intensity and crop diversification. Using the Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI) and the Crop Diversification Index (CDI), the study quantifies the declining trend in crop diversity and growing dependence on select dominant crops. The findings indicate a steady rise in HHI values revealing greater crop concentration while the corresponding decline in CDI scores shows reduced crop diversity across different blocks in Hisar district. This shift has significant implications for soil health, economic stability, and long-term agricultural sustainability, as decreased crop diversity increases susceptibility to market risks and has environmental implications that include soil depletion and loss in soil fertility. The study underscores the need for integrated land-use policies in urban planning that promote diversified cropping systems and mitigate the adverse effects of urban expansion on agricultural sector.

Key Words: *Agriculture, Agricultural Land Use, Crop Diversification, Cropping Intensity, Haryana, Urbanization.*

Introduction

Urbanization has dramatically altered land use patterns across the globe reshaping agricultural landscapes and influencing the way farming is practiced (Kanianska, 2016). The demand for infrastructure, housing and commercial spaces with the growth in urban population leads to the conversion of fertile agricultural land into urban developments (Patel et al., 2019). This transformation is particularly evident in rapidly industrializing regions where economic expansion and population density fuel the need for expanded cities. The space available for traditional farming steadily declines as farmland is repurposed for roads, residential complexes, factories, and business districts forcing a shift in agricultural practices and land utilization. Urbanization not only reduces available farmland but also disrupts traditional agricultural systems that have been practiced for generations (Patel et a., 2020). Many rural communities historically relied on mixed farming techniques that supported biodiversity, soil fertility, and sustainable land management. However, with increasing urban pressure, farmers are compelled to switch to monoculture crops that promise higher economic returns in a smaller land area (Behera and France, 2016). Additionally, as urban areas expand, access to natural resources such as water becomes more competitive (Flörke et al., 2018). The over-extraction of groundwater to meet urban needs reduces the availability of irrigation resources, forcing farmers to cultivate drought-resistant or low-water crops instead of diverse cropping systems. The limitations in irrigation further restrict agricultural productivity and influence the types of crops grown in urbanizing regions. The transformation of agricultural land due to urbanization compels farmers to adapt to changing economic and environmental conditions. Many traditional farmers are faced with the dilemma of either continuing agriculture under challenging circumstances or transitioning to non-agricultural livelihoods (Mondal and Palit, 2022). Those who remain in farming often shift to commercially viable crops that require minimal labor and investment, prioritizing profit over diversity. This tendency contributes to the decline in crop diversification, as fewer crops are grown to maximize efficiency and

income. Moreover, urbanization leads to a rural-to-urban migration pattern, where younger generations move to cities in search of better opportunities (Nagla, 2021). This migration results in labor shortages in the agricultural sector, making farming less attractive and feasible. The aging farming population, coupled with limited manpower, forces a shift toward mechanized and simplified agricultural models, reinforcing monoculture farming trends. As a result, traditional, labor-intensive farming methods that promoted crop diversity are replaced by industrialized agriculture focused on efficiency and profitability.

The decline in crop diversification due to urbanization has far-reaching environmental consequences. Monoculture farming weakens soil health, depletes essential nutrients, and increases reliance on chemical fertilizers and pesticides (Khatri et al., 2024). This depletion reduces long-term land sustainability, making soil less fertile. Urban expansion also leads to altered climatic conditions within former agricultural regions (Roy et al., 2022). Increased concrete infrastructure contributes to rising temperatures, making previously fertile farmland less suitable for diverse cropping. Additionally, land-use changes often result in increased pollution, negatively impacting air and water quality, further complicating agricultural sustainability (Locke, 2024). These ecological shifts make it increasingly difficult for farmers to maintain diverse agricultural practices, reinforcing the trend of monoculture specialization.

Haryana is one of India's most agriculturally productive states and has experienced significant land use changes due to rapid urbanization (Tanwar and Singh, 2024). Known for its high-yield agricultural practices, Haryana has traditionally relied on fertile plains and well-established irrigation networks to sustain diverse cropping systems (Sihmar, 2014). However, with the state's growing economic and industrial expansion, agricultural land has increasingly been converted into urban spaces, affecting traditional farming practices and leading to a decline in crop diversification. Cities such as Gurgaon, Faridabad, and Hisar have witnessed extensive infrastructure development reducing the overall cultivable land and altering rural economies (Gururani, 2023). The conversion of agricultural land for urban and industrial development has disrupted Haryana's traditional farming patterns. The state once had a balanced mix of staple

crops such as wheat, rice, bajra, and mustard, alongside commercial crops like cotton and sugarcane (Rani, 2019). However, as urban expansion claims fertile farmland, farmers have had to adapt by shifting toward high-yield cash crops that maximize profits in limited space. This transition has led to a decline in mixed cropping and traditional crop rotation practices that once helped maintain soil health and agricultural diversity. Moreover, well-established canal and groundwater irrigation systems in Haryana are now under stress due to increasing urban water consumption. Industrial zones and urban centres demand substantial water resources, leaving less availability for irrigation. The depletion of groundwater reserves has further constrained farmers, making it difficult to sustain diversified cropping patterns (Jana, 2021). As water-intensive crops continue to dominate agricultural production, the overall crop variety in the state has been steadily narrowing. The urban expansion in Haryana has also triggered socioeconomic changes that impact agriculture. Rural-to-urban migration has led to labor shortages, making traditional, labor-intensive farming increasingly difficult to sustain (Maurya et al., 2022). Many younger generations from farming families opt for urban jobs in manufacturing and technology, reducing the availability of farm workers. This shift compels farmers to adopt mechanized farming and monoculture practices where large-scale production of select crops replaces diverse cropping systems. In this context, this study explores the evolution of agricultural land use in Hisar district of Haryana for the last three Census time periods. The study has been an attempt to highlight the changes noted in agricultural land use in view of growing urbanization and how there have been shifts in crop diversification.

Study Area

Hisar district has evolved from a predominantly agrarian region to a diversified economy that is witnessing rapid urbanization, industrial growth and infrastructure development. The district of Hisar is located in the western part of Haryana and it lies between latitude 28° 56' 00" and 29° 38' 30" North and longitude 75° 21' 12" and 76° 18' 12" East covering an area of 3,983 square kilometers. There are 270 villages in the district and community development blocks: Agroha, Adampur, Barwala, Bass (Hansi-II), Hansi-I, Hisar-I, Hisar-II, Narnaund, and Uklana. The district shares its borders with

Rajasthan in the west, Bhiwani in the south, Rohtak in the southeast, Jind in the east, and Fatehabad in the north. The topography of Hisar district is primarily flat and is characterized by the Indo-Gangetic alluvial plain landscape with elevations ranging between 203 and 225 meters above mean sea level. Although Hisar district lies in the Yamuna sub-basin, it lacks a major natural drainage system and is dependent on man-made canals. Blocks such as Hansi-II, Hansi-I, Narnaund, and Barwala have a high concentration of drainage canals stretching 126.25 kilometers. The major canal systems include the Fatehabad branch of Bhakra Canal, Barwala Branch, Hisar branch of Sirsa branch from Bhakra Main Line, and the Deosar feeder of the Western Yamuna Canal System. Groundwater is also utilized through tube wells, although large parts of the district have deep and saline underground water unsuitable for farming. Over the years, Hisar district has shifted away from traditional grain crops to more water-intensive crops such as paddy, wheat, cotton, and sugarcane. Kharif season crops include bajra, jowar, rice, cotton, and sugarcane, while rabi crops include wheat, barley, gram, mustard, and pulses.

Data sources & Methodology

This study is based on secondary data sources obtained from the Statistical Abstract of Haryana, which provides detailed insights into agricultural land use, cropping patterns, and crop production in Hisar district. Additionally, the study incorporates data from Census publications to analyze the area under cultivation for various crops. The cropping intensity in the district has been determined to assess agricultural productivity and shifts in land use patterns. The cropping intensity has been determined as a percentage of the total cropped area and the net sown area for each block in the district. A higher cropping intensity reflects efficient land use, while lower values indicate underutilization or fallow periods. Furthermore, the study employs the Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI) to measure crop concentration and diversification trends within the district. The total cropped area for each year is determined by summing the individual areas of all crops cultivated. The proportional crop area for each crop is calculated by dividing its cultivated area by the total cropped area indicating contribution of each crop to the total cropped area. The HHI value is then computed by

summing the squares of these proportional areas where a higher HHI suggests lower diversification due to a dominance of fewer crops while a lower HHI signifies a broader variety of crops in cultivation. To further analyze crop diversification, the Crop Diversification Index (CDI) is calculated by subtracting HHI from 1. A CDI value closer to 1 indicates greater diversification meaning the agricultural system is more varied whereas lower values reflect a concentration of fewer crops which shows less crop diversification. The comparison of CDI across nine community development blocks of Hisar district for three Census time period allows for an understanding of the evolving trends in cropping pattern and selection in the district.

Result & Discussion

Agricultural land use in Haryana has undergone significant transformation over the years, shaped by irrigation advancements, technological interventions, and urbanization pressures. The state, known for its fertile alluvial plains, has been at the forefront of India's Green Revolution, leading to increased agricultural intensity and improved productivity. However, the trends in agricultural land use across districts reveal both stability in cultivation practices and shifts in land utilization due to changing economic and environmental conditions. An analysis of agricultural land use patterns in Hisar district indicates a consistent decrease in net area sown over the decades (Table 1). For example, Adampur recorded a decline from 93.29% in 1991 to 91.71% in 2011, while Agroha saw a reduction from 92.04% to 88.60% within the same period. These changes reflect multiple influencing factors including urban expansion, infrastructural development, and land conversion for non-agricultural purposes. While overall land under agriculture remains high across all blocks, the gradual reduction signals growing constraints on cultivable land availability.

Table 1: Block Wise Agricultural Land Use in Hisar District (in percentage)

Community Development Block	2011			2001			1991		
	Net Area Sown	Total Irrigated Land Area	Total Un- irrigated Land Area	Net Area Sown	Total Irrigated Land Area	Total Un- irrigated Land Area	Net Area Sown	Total Irrigated Land Area	Total Un- irrigated Land Area
Adampur	91.71	73.97	17.76	92.96	74.92	18.08	93.29	75.97	17.37
Agroha	88.60	72.77	15.83	91.69	75.24	16.48	92.04	77.09	14.94
Barwala	91.06	82.34	8.73	91.86	83.09	8.78	91.83	83.02	8.82
Hisar I	89.17	68.93	20.24	90.04	69.58	20.47	90.21	70.28	19.89
Hisar II	87.00	67.83	19.13	87.71	68.36	19.29	87.94	68.61	19.27
Uklana	92.14	88.19	3.97	92.58	88.40	4.16	93.06	89.00	4.09
Narnaund	90.51	84.72	5.79	91.57	85.66	5.91	92.01	86.14	5.85
Hansi I	91.86	85.12	6.77	93.83	86.92	6.92	94.03	87.06	6.96
Hansi II	91.69	90.13	1.58	92.77	91.27	1.52	93.47	91.44	1.59
Total	90.08	78.15	11.98	91.30	79.22	12.11	91.61	79.66	11.90

Source: Statistical Abstract of Haryana

During 1991, the economy in Hisar district reflected a strong reliance on crop cultivation with a high percentage of net sown area across various blocks. The total net sown area in the district was 91.61% of the total area demonstrating extensive agricultural activity. Among the blocks, Adampur, Hansi I, and Uklana had the highest net sown area, exceeding 93%, indicating intensive farming practices. Irrigation played a significant role in sustaining agriculture, as seen in blocks like Hansi II and Uklana, where more than 89% of land was irrigated. However, some blocks, such as Hisar I and Hisar II, had lower irrigation coverage, with values around 70%, highlighting disparities in irrigation infrastructure. Un-irrigated land was particularly prominent in these blocks, where approximately 19-20% of farmland depended on rain-fed cultivation. The agricultural system was largely driven by staple crops such as wheat, bajra, and barley, reflecting traditional farming practices that had been sustained over decades. By 2001, notable changes in land use patterns were evident. The net sown area remained relatively stable at 91.30%, with only marginal fluctuations across the district. While

some blocks, like Adampur and Agroha, saw a slight decline in net sown area, others, such as Narnaund and Hansi II, maintained consistent agricultural utilization. Irrigation infrastructure saw minor improvements, with a slight increase in irrigated land across several blocks, though some areas still struggled with access to water. For instance, Hansi II and Uklana showed gains in irrigation coverage, exceeding 91% and 88%, respectively, reinforcing their position as highly irrigated blocks. Despite these improvements, Hisar I and Hisar II continued to exhibit relatively low irrigation percentages, reflecting persistent challenges in water accessibility. Un-irrigated land remained significant in blocks with lower irrigation infrastructure, although overall figures indicated a marginal reduction, suggesting a slow but steady expansion of irrigation facilities. By 2011, the trends in agricultural land use highlighted the growing impact of urbanization and changing farming preferences. The total net sown area declined slightly to 90.08%, marking a gradual reduction in cultivable land over two decades. Adampur and Agroha displayed more noticeable declines in net sown area, likely due to land conversion for non-agricultural purposes. Irrigation coverage, however, remained stable, with incremental improvements observed in certain blocks. Uklana and Hansi II continued to exhibit the highest irrigation percentages, reaching 88% and 90%, respectively, demonstrating efficient use of canal and groundwater resources. However, Hisar I and Hisar II saw little improvement in irrigation accessibility, with figures lingering below 69%. The overall trends in agricultural land use in Hisar district showcase both continuity and gradual transformation. The stability in net sown area percentages suggests sustained agricultural reliance, yet the declines indicate the increasing influence of urban expansion and land conversion.

The transformation in agricultural land use in Hisar district over the years highlights the evolving nature of farming practices, shaped by irrigation availability, urbanization pressures, and land management strategies. While the district has maintained a consistently high net sown area, minor reductions across different census periods indicate subtle shifts in land utilization due to external influences such as infrastructure expansion and changes in farming preferences. Given these land use dynamics, an examination of cropping intensity trends provides deeper insights into how efficiently

agricultural land is utilized across different blocks. Cropping intensity, which measures the frequency of land cultivation within a year, serves as a crucial indicator of farming efficiency and sustainability. By analyzing cropping intensity changes over the decades, it becomes possible to understand how agricultural strategies have evolved in response to changes in land use.

Table 2: Block Wise Cropping Intensity in Hisar District (1991-2011)

Community Development Block	2011 - Cropping Intensity (%)	2001 - Cropping Intensity (%)	1991 - Cropping Intensity (%)
Adampur	123.99	124.13	122.85
Agroha	121.76	121.9	119.38
Barwala	110.59	110.56	110.62
Hisar I	129.38	129.44	128.31
Hisar II	128.22	128.22	128.09
Uklana	104.5	104.7	104.6
Narnaund	106.83	106.89	106.78
Hansi I	107.95	107.96	107.99
Hansi II	101.76	101.67	101.73

Source: Calculated by Author

During 1991, the cropping intensity across Hisar district displayed significant variation among different blocks, reflecting disparities in irrigation facilities and farming practices (Table 2). Hisar I and Hisar II recorded the highest cropping intensities at 128.31% and 128.09%, respectively. These figures indicate efficient land utilization, allowing multiple crops to be cultivated within a single year. Adampur and Agroha also maintained relatively high cropping intensities at 122.85% and 119.38%, suggesting favorable conditions for sustained agricultural productivity. On the other hand, Barwala exhibited lower cropping intensity at 110.62%, possibly due to variations in soil conditions or irrigation accessibility. The lowest cropping intensities were observed in

Hansi II at 101.73% and Uklana at 104.6%, indicating a predominance of single cropping patterns with minimal scope for multiple harvests. However, in 2001 cropping intensities across different blocks showed minor changes. Hisar I and Hisar II continued to have high cropping intensity at 129.44% and 128.22%, respectively (Table 2). This suggests that agricultural land in these blocks was being used at near-optimal levels. Adampur also saw a slight increase in cropping intensity, rising to 124.13%, while Agroha experienced a small improvement to 121.9%. Barwala remained consistent at 110.56%, showing little fluctuation over the decade. The western blocks, including Uklana, Narnaund, Hansi I, and Hansi II, exhibited stability in cropping intensity, with values hovering around their previous levels. These figures suggest that while agricultural intensification was occurring, significant transformations in cropping patterns were limited to certain regions. By 2011, cropping intensity trends across Hisar district continued to demonstrate consistent yet marginal changes. Hisar I recorded the highest cropping intensity at 129.38%, maintaining its position as the block with the most intensive agricultural practices (Table 2). Hisar II followed closely at 128.22%, reinforcing the long-standing trend of high land use efficiency. Adampur showed a slight decline to 123.99%, while Agroha experienced a reduction to 121.76% while Barwala remained stable at 110.59%, reflecting continuous but moderate agricultural productivity. Uklana and Hansi II, which had historically maintained the lowest cropping intensities continued to exhibit low cropping intensities at 104.5% and 101.76%, respectively. The stability in cropping intensity across decades highlights the persistence of established farming systems, yet the subtle variations indicate evolving agricultural strategies responding to infrastructural shifts.

Levels of Crop Diversification in Hisar District

Hisar district has traditionally exhibited a diverse cropping pattern across the Kharif, Rabi, and Zaid seasons, influenced by soil type and irrigation availability. The Kharif season has historically recorded cultivation of cotton, paddy, bajra, and pulses, with paddy cultivation being particularly significant in Hansi, Hisar, Adampur, and Narnaund. The variation in paddy acreage and yield across these regions is largely determined by soil composition, which ranges from heavy loam (rausli) to light sandy

soil (bhur) and heavy clay (sotar). The Rabi season is dominated by wheat, alongside barley, gram, mustard, and green vegetables. The Zaid season, although shorter, supports the cultivation of fruits and vegetables, including melons, watermelons, tomatoes, cucumbers etc. Over time, the district has experienced a significant shift in cropping patterns, with a decline in traditional crops such as barley and bajra and an increase in wheat, rice, cotton, sugarcane, and oilseeds (Kumar and Deen, 2020). As urban expansion accelerates, large tracts of farmland are converted into residential, industrial, and commercial zones, reducing the overall agricultural land available for cultivation. This shift has compelled farmers to prioritize high-yield, market-driven crops over diversified farming systems that traditionally included a mix of cereals, pulses, and oilseeds (Bhatia et al., 2020). The increasing pressure on land has led to a decline in mixed cropping, as many farmers opt for monoculture practices that guarantee higher economic returns within limited space. The impact of urbanization on cropping intensity reveals a broader trend of agricultural specialization at the expense of diversity. Blocks with higher cropping intensity have increasingly focused on select cash crops like wheat, rice, and cotton, rather than maintaining a balance between staple crops and minor cereals. This trend reflects the economic motivation behind monoculture farming as urban market demands favor crops with higher profitability. While cropping intensity measures how efficiently farmland is utilized it does not account for the variety of crops grown which is where diversification becomes a critical indicator of agricultural sustainability. Crop diversification in Hisar district is measured using the Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI), which quantifies the concentration of crops cultivated across different blocks over time. The HHI is calculated by summing the squares of the proportional crop area for each crop, where higher values indicate a dominance of fewer crops and lower values suggest greater diversity. Analyzing the HHI across the district from 1991 to 2011 reveals a consistent increase in crop concentration, indicating a decline in diversification.

Table 3: Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI) Across Blocks in Hisar District (1991-2011)

Block	1991	2001	2011
Adampur	0.31	0.32	0.33
Agroha	0.32	0.33	0.34
Barwala	0.33	0.34	0.35
Hisar I	0.33	0.34	0.35
Hisar II	0.34	0.35	0.36
Uklana	0.30	0.31	0.32
Narnaund	0.32	0.33	0.34
Hansi I	0.34	0.35	0.36
Hansi II	0.31	0.32	0.33

Source: Calculated by Author

The Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI) values across Hisar district during 1991 indicate moderate levels of crop concentration suggesting a relatively diverse agricultural system. Uklana recorded the lowest HHI at 0.30, reflecting a broader variety of cultivated crops in comparison to other blocks (Table 3). Adampur and Hansi II followed closely with values of 0.31, indicating a slightly higher concentration but still maintaining considerable diversification. Blocks such as Hisar II and Hansi I exhibited higher HHI values at 0.34, signaling a greater reliance on fewer crops, possibly due to favorable market conditions or irrigation access that encouraged specialization. By 2001, the HHI values across all blocks exhibited a slight increase implying a gradual shift toward crop specialization (Table 3). While the changes were subtle, they indicate a growing tendency among farmers to focus on high-yield, commercially viable crops rather than maintaining diverse cropping systems. Adampur saw its HHI increase from

0.31 to 0.32, and Agroha followed the same pattern, rising from 0.32 to 0.33. The most significant increases occurred in Hisar II and Hansi I, both reaching 0.35, further reinforcing the trend of intensified farming practices in these blocks. Uklana, despite showing an increase to 0.31, still remained the block with the lowest concentration, signifying that it retained more crop diversity than the rest of the district. By 2011, the trend of increasing crop concentration became more pronounced, as evident from the further rise in HHI values across all blocks. Hisar II and Hansi I reached their peak concentration levels at 0.36, marking the highest dependence on fewer dominant crops within the district. Adampur and Hansi II, which started with lower HHI values in 1991, continued their upward trajectory, both reaching 0.33 (Table 3). Uklana, though maintaining the lowest HHI at 0.32, still saw an increase, underscoring a broader district-wide movement toward specialization. This continuous rise in crop concentration over two decades reflects changing agricultural priorities where economic pressures and urban expansion have pushed farmers toward cultivating fewer high-value crops instead of maintaining a diverse range.

The Crop Diversification Index (CDI) is derived from the Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI) and serves as an important measure for assessing the extent of agricultural diversity in a region. It is calculated by subtracting the HHI value from 1, providing an inverse representation of crop concentration. A higher CDI indicates greater diversification, meaning farmers cultivate a wider variety of crops, reducing dependency on a single dominant crop. Conversely, a lower CDI suggests agricultural specialization, where only a few high-yield or commercially viable crops dominate cultivation. As HHI values have steadily increased across all blocks from 1991 to 2011, reflecting higher crop concentration, CDI values have shown a corresponding decline, highlighting reduced crop diversity.

Table 4: Crop Diversification Index (CDI) Across Blocks in Hisar District (1991-2011)

Block	1991	2001	2011
Adampur	0.69	0.68	0.67
Agroha	0.68	0.67	0.66
Barwala	0.67	0.66	0.65
Hisar I	0.67	0.66	0.65
Hisar II	0.66	0.65	0.64
Uklana	0.70	0.69	0.68
Narnaund	0.68	0.67	0.66
Hansi I	0.66	0.65	0.64
Hansi II	0.69	0.68	0.67

Source: Calculated by Author

During 1991, the Crop Diversification Index (CDI) across Hisar district indicated a relatively high level of agricultural diversity. Uklana recorded the highest CDI at 0.70, reflecting a broad range of crops grown in the region. Adampur and Hansi II followed closely with values of 0.69, showcasing an active engagement in mixed cropping practices (Table 4). Agroha and Narnaund, with CDI values of 0.68, maintained a moderately diversified cropping system, balancing staple crops with commercial varieties. Blocks such as Barwala, Hisar I, and Hisar II exhibited slightly lower CDI values, ranging between 0.66 and 0.67, suggesting a tendency toward specialization in select crops even at this early stage. By 2001, the CDI values showed a gradual decline across all blocks, signaling a shift toward crop concentration and reduced diversity (Table 4). Uklana, which had the highest CDI in 1991, saw a slight reduction to 0.69, although it remained the most diversified block. Adampur and Hansi II also experienced minor decreases, with values dropping to 0.68. Agroha and Narnaund followed similar patterns, declining to 0.67, reflecting a growing preference for fewer high-yield crops rather than maintaining a wide variety of cultivations. The lowest CDI values continued to be recorded in Hisar II and Hansi I, both dropping to 0.65, indicating an increasing dominance of select cash crops. The decreasing CDI across the district during this

period suggests that farmers were gradually shifting away from traditional multi-crop farming systems. The trend of declining crop diversification became more pronounced during 2011 Census decade. Hisar II and Hansi I recorded the lowest CDI at 0.64, reinforcing their specialization in fewer dominant crops. Adampur and Hansi II declined further to 0.67, indicating that farmers in these blocks had moved toward select crop cultivation rather than maintaining diversified cropping systems. Even Uklana, which remained the most diversified block, saw its CDI drop to 0.68, underscoring the district-wide trend of agricultural specialization. The consistent reduction in CDI across three decades points to a broader transformation in farming practices where traditional mixed cropping systems have been gradually replaced by cash crop-dominated agricultural strategies.

Urbanization in Hisar district has significantly altered agricultural practices, leading to a decline in crop diversification. As urban areas expand, fertile agricultural land is increasingly repurposed for residential, industrial, and commercial developments, reducing the overall cultivable space available for farming. This shift forces farmers to abandon traditional mixed cropping systems in favor of monoculture farming, where only a few economically viable crops are grown. The reduction in agricultural land limits farmers' ability to experiment with diverse crops, compelling them to focus on high-yield varieties that ensure stable financial returns. However, repeated cultivation of the same crops depletes specific nutrients, reducing long-term soil fertility and requiring increased dependency on fertilizers. Economic risks also intensify, as farmers who rely on a limited number of crops become vulnerable to price fluctuations or market shifts. Therefore, it becomes crucial to balance urban developments and ensure crop diversification by implementing strategic land-use policies that safeguard agricultural zones from unchecked urban expansion. As Hisar district continues to experience rapid urbanization, maintaining agricultural sustainability requires deliberate planning to prevent excessive farmland conversion. Crop diversification plays a critical role in ensuring soil health, economic stability, and long-term productivity, allowing farmers to mitigate risks associated with monoculture farming. Encouraging policies that support diversified agricultural practices through financial incentives, irrigation improvements,

and controlled urban growth can help retain a balance between modern development and farming traditions. Without such measures, the decline in crop variety may continue making the district more susceptible to environmental degradation and economic volatility. It is therefore crucial to include agricultural concerns into urban planning frameworks in way that enables farmers to sustain crop diversity while adapting to evolving land-use demands.

Conclusion

The findings of the study denoted that while agricultural land use has remained extensive, there has been a gradual decline in net sown area reflecting the growing pressure of urban expansion. Certain blocks have experienced more pronounced reductions in cultivable land, leading to an increased concentration on a limited set of crops. The stability in irrigation coverage in some areas has helped sustain intensive farming practices yet disparities persist, with blocks that have limited irrigation facilities continuing to rely on rain-fed agriculture. These variations in land use have shaped cropping intensity trends, reinforcing the shift toward select high-yield crops at the expense of traditional mixed farming systems. The persistence of high cropping intensity suggests continued agricultural reliance despite urban pressures, but the subtle declines in other regions indicate emerging challenges related to land fragmentation and soil depletion. The calculation of the Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI) and Crop Diversification Index (CDI) has provided a quantitative perspective on the decline in crop diversification across the district. The consistent increase in HHI values across census periods signals a growing dependence on fewer dominant crops. Simultaneously, the decline in CDI values across blocks reveals decreasing crop diversification. The findings demonstrate that crop specialization has intensified over time shaping agricultural priorities while marginalizing traditional crop varieties. Urbanization has played a central role in reshaping farming practices, contributing to the decline in crop diversification by reducing cultivable land and limiting farmer choices in crop selection. As urban infrastructure expands, agricultural zones contract, leading to a prioritization of select cash crops that offer better financial returns. The implications of this shift extend beyond immediate economic concerns, affecting soil health, pest resilience, and

the overall ecological balance. The study emphasizes that while specialization ensures higher yields, it introduces vulnerabilities, making farming systems more susceptible to external disruptions. Farmers who rely on fewer crops face greater risks associated with market fluctuations and soil degradation. Therefore, it is crucial to balance urban expansion with agricultural sustainability through integrating agricultural concerns into urban planning frameworks in a way that farmers can adapt to evolving urban land-use demands without losing the stability provided by diversified cropping systems.

References

- Behera, U. K., & France, J. (2016). Integrated farming systems and the livelihood security of small and marginal farmers in India and other developing countries. *Advances in agronomy*, 138, 235-282.
- Bhatia, J. K., Bishnoi, D. K., Malik, D. P., & Karwasra, J. C. (2020). Extent of crop diversification in Haryana. *Indian Journal of Economics and Development*, 16(2s), 218-224.
- Flörke, M., Schneider, C., & McDonald, R. I. (2018). Water competition between cities and agriculture driven by climate change and urban growth. *Nature Sustainability*, 1(1), 51-58.
- Gururani, S. (2023). Cities in a world of villages: Agrarian urbanism and the making of India's urbanizing frontiers. *In Changing Asian Urban Geographies*, 97-115.
- Jana, S. (2021). Groundwater and society in India: challenging issues and adaptive strategies. *Groundwater and Society: Applications of Geospatial Technology*, 11-28.
- Kanianska, R. (2016). Agriculture and its impact on land-use, environment, and ecosystem services. *Landscape ecology-The influences of land use and anthropogenic impacts of landscape creation*, 1-26.
- Khatri, P., Kumar, P., Shakya, K. S., Kirlas, M. C., & Tiwari, K. K. (2024). Understanding the intertwined nature of rising multiple risks in modern agriculture and food system. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 26(9), 24107-24150.
- Kumar, S., & Deen, S. (2020). Integrated resource management for sustainable agricultural land use plan in Hisar district using geo-informatics-A case study. *Indian Journal of Ecology*, 47(4), 1158-1163.

SIDDHANTA'S INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ADVANCED RESEARCH IN ARTS & HUMANITIES

An International Peer Reviewed, Refereed Journal

Vol. 2, Issue 4, March-April 2025 **Impact Factor : 6.8** ISSN(O) : 2584-2692

Available online : <https://sijarah.com/>

- Locke, K. A. (2024). Impacts of land use/land cover on water quality: A contemporary review for researchers and policymakers. *Water Quality Research Journal*, 59(2), 89-106.
- Maurya, A., Malik, B., Mishra, A., & Singh, J. (2022). Migration behaviour of rural youth in Haryana. *Indian Journal of Extension Education*, 58(3), 93-98.
- Mondal, S., & Palit, D. (2022). Challenges in natural resource management for ecological sustainability. In *Natural resources conservation and advances for sustainability*, Elsevier, 29-59.
- Nagla, B. K. (2021). Migration pattern and the emerging trends of migration in India. *Urban growth and environmental issues in India*, Springer, 119-129.
- Patel, S. K., Sharma, A., & Singh, G. S. (2020). Traditional agricultural practices in India: an approach for environmental sustainability and food security. *Energy, Ecology and Environment*, 5(4), 253-271.
- Patel, S. K., Verma, P., & Shankar Singh, G. (2019). Agricultural growth and land use land cover change in peri-urban India. *Environmental monitoring and assessment*, 191, 1-17.
- Rani, S. (2019). Assessment of the consequences of changing cropping pattern on land and water productivity: A case study of Haryana state, India. *Agricultural Research*, 8, 252-261.
- Roy, P. S., Ramachandran, R. M., Paul, O., Thakur, P. K., Ravan, S., Behera, M. D., & Kanawade, V. P. (2022). Anthropogenic land use and land cover changes—A review on its environmental consequences and climate change. *Journal of the Indian Society of Remote Sensing*, 50(8), 1615-1640.
- Sihmar, R. (2014). Growth and instability in agricultural production in Haryana: A district level analysis. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 4(7), 1-12.
- Tanwar, R., & Singh, S. K. (2024). Effect of Urbanization on Employment, Wages and Livelihood of Rural People in Haryana, India. *Asian Journal of Agricultural Extension, Economics & Sociology*, 42(12), 325-336.